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Advanced Gas Equation with Charge Relationship

The existing gas equation provides a relationship between only the pressure, temperature, and quantity of gas flowing in a system, which limits all the existing turbines to work only on the velocity of the gas. With the addition of the charge parameter, energy can also be extracted from the pressure of the gas and not just the velocity.

The Advanced gas equation is classified under SIU.